

TOURISM BASED ON THE HARMONY OF HISTORICAL SITES AND NATURAL LANDSCAPES: A CASE STUDY OF TOURIST VILLAGES IN THE FORISH DISTRICT

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Abstract. *This article explores the establishment and operation of the “Mojrum Open-Air Museum” in the Jizzakh region of the Republic of Uzbekistan, within the framework of sustainable tourism development and rural tourism practices. Emphasizing the integration of historical and archaeological heritage with natural landscapes, the study highlights the significance of harmonizing cultural and environmental resources to enhance tourism in the region. Particular attention is given to potential challenges that may emerge during the construction and organizational phases of the museum. The research is conducted as part of the practical project titled “Increasing the Tourist Potential of the Forish District Based on the Harmony of Historical Sites and Natural Places” (Project No. ALM – 202403110244).*

Keywords: *Farish, sustainable tourism, route, mahalla, rural, tourist flow.*

Introduction. In the contemporary context, enhancing the positive socio-economic impacts of tourism while mitigating its negative consequences has become a key priority. This has led to increased focus on modern research that provides a scientific and theoretical foundation for the sustainable development of the tourism sector. As tourism emerges as a critical driver of sustainable development, examining the factors that contribute to its competitiveness is gaining prominence as a complex and evolving area of economic inquiry. Accordingly, the analysis of tourism as a catalyst for economic growth, national economic competitiveness, and improvements in population income and living standards underscores the urgent need for a comprehensive study of sustainability issues. Moreover, the integration and widespread application of information and communication technologies in this field is increasingly recognized as essential to achieving long-term development goals.

When addressing the concept of *mahalla* (rural) tourism, it is essential to first clarify the meaning and scope of the term. In contemporary domestic and international academic literature, various definitions of this emerging form of tourism can be found, reflecting its innovative nature not only within Uzbekistan but also in the global context. *Mahalla* (rural) tourism may be understood as an umbrella term encompassing a wide range of both organized and informal tourism activities conducted in rural areas. It integrates cultural, ecological, and community-based experiences, offering tourists authentic encounters with rural lifestyles and traditions. At present, *mahalla* (rural) tourism constitutes a significant segment of the global tourism industry, accounting for an estimated 12–30% of the total international tourist flow.

Consequently, it has become an urgent priority for countries to develop and implement targeted policies aimed at enhancing competitiveness and ensuring sustainability, in order to fully harness the long-term potential of the tourism sector.

Methodology. Currently, there are over 100 *mahallas* and villages across Uzbekistan that possess significant tourism potential and the capacity to develop various promising forms of tourism. Among them, the *mahallas* of Okhum, Sayyod, Dostlik, and Uchkuloch—located in the Forish district of the Jizzakh region—hold particular significance, having been officially designated as "Tourism *mahallas*" due to their cultural, historical, and natural attractions.

The Forish district, located in the Jizzakh region in the central part of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is distinguished by its remarkable natural beauty, including mountainous terrains, unique lake landscapes, and a rich historical and cultural heritage. Despite these abundant resources, their potential remains underutilized within the tourism sector. In the current context, the development of both domestic and international tourism has been identified as a strategic priority in Uzbekistan. In this regard, the Forish district offers substantial opportunities to enhance tourism potential through the integrated and harmonious development of its historical landmarks and natural attractions.

The Forish district was officially established on February 9, 1935, through the unification of several rural councils, including Poyariq (from Gallaorol district), Sintob, Katta Ogach, and Ishtikhan (from Nurota district), as well as Forish, Uchma, Yangikishlok, and Osmonsay (from Jizzakh district) [1]. Initially, Forish district was part of the Samarkand region; in 1964, it was transferred to the Syrdarya region, and since 1974, it has been part of the Jizzakh region. In 1962, the district was temporarily dissolved and its territories were merged into the Nurota and Jizzakh districts, but it was re-established as a separate administrative unit in 1964. The population of the district is ethnically diverse, consisting primarily of Uzbeks, Tajiks, Kazakhs, and representatives of other nationalities.

The Forish district shares its northern and northeastern borders with the Republic of Kazakhstan, while to the east it is bordered by the Mirzachul and Arnasay districts. To the southeast lie the Zafarabad and Jizzakh districts, with Galla-Aral district to the south, and the Samarkand and Navoi regions to the west. The total area of the district is 9,893 square kilometers, making it geographically larger than several European countries, including Luxembourg, Liechtenstein, Monaco, and Malta [2]. Following the administrative division of the Chirakchi district in the Kashkadarya region into Chirakchi and Kokdala, Forish has become the largest district in Uzbekistan in terms of land area. Notably, the size of Forish district alone is nearly equivalent to that of the entire Andijan region [3].

The Forish district borders the Shymkent region of the Republic of Kazakhstan to the north and northeast, Jizzakh and Zafarabad districts to the east, Gallaorol district to the south, and Kushrabot and Nurota districts to the west. The district's administrative center is the town of Yangikishlok. Located in the northwestern part of the Jizzakh region, Forish features a diverse landscape that includes lowlands, mountains, hills, and the Nurata and Pistali ranges. The Nurata range rises gradually from the northeast (230–250 meters) to the southwest (1,400–2,000 meters), with its highest point being Hayotbashi peak, which stands at 2,169 meters above sea level. To the southwest, the district is bordered by the Nurata mountains, as well as the Kuytash, Baliklitog, and Pistalitog ranges. The Forish district, primarily situated in the northern part of the Nurata mountains, adjoins the vast Kyzylkum desert. The region experiences a continental climate, characterized by hot, dry summers and cool winters.

Several rivers, including Ustikhonsoy, Osmonsay, Ilonchisoy, Ukhumsay, Hayotsay, Oktoshsoy, Kattasoy, Chorvoqsoy, Ukhumsay, Mojrumsay, and others, flow from the Nurota

mountains and are utilized for irrigating the loess slopes at the foot of the mountains. Additionally, the district is home to the "Forestry" and "Nurota State Reserve," both of which are located within its territory, contributing to the preservation of local biodiversity and the sustainable management of natural resources.

The district's natural landscape is predominantly characterized by mountainous terrains, adirs (hilly uplands), and the Aydar-Arnasay lake system (including Lake Tuzkan), as well as extensive desert areas. These diverse geographical features, combined with the region's rich ethnographic heritage and abundance of historical sites, create highly favorable conditions for the development of ecotourism, mountain tourism, and historical-ethnographic tourism.

The etymology of the toponym *Farish* has attracted the attention of numerous scholars, leading to a variety of interpretations and hypotheses. According to the *National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan*, one widely held local belief suggests that the name originated from the city of "Paris," which Amir Temur purportedly intended to establish near Samarkand. Over time, this name is thought to have undergone phonetic transformation in the local dialect, evolving into *Farish*, *Farish*, and eventually *Farish*.

In reality, this folk interpretation lacks scholarly credibility. Firstly, there is no mention in the written records of Amir Temur's era or in subsequent historical sources to support the claim that the name *Farish* was derived from *Paris*. Secondly, even the *National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan* clarifies that this notion is speculative and not grounded in historical fact. Thirdly, the original village from which the district takes its name is still referred to as *Porasht* in the local dialect, rather than *Farish*, further undermining the folk etymology [4].

The toponym *Farish* has also been interpreted by scholar B. Urinbaev, who proposed that the name derives from a combination of the Sogdian elements *far*, *par*, *bar*, or *var*, meaning "upper," and the Turkic and Mongolic elements *sin* or *shin*, meaning "peoples." According to this interpretation, *Farish* or *Fashin* would translate as "the peoples living above." However, this hypothesis has been met with skepticism by many geographers and linguists, who consider it speculative and lacking sufficient linguistic or historical evidence. As a result, the true origin of the term *Farish* likely lies elsewhere and remains a subject requiring further scholarly investigation.

The village of Porasht is situated approximately 30 kilometers northwest of Bogdan, the administrative center of the district, on the left side of the Jizzakh–Nurota highway. The local population primarily communicates in Uzbek and Tajik. According to oral accounts preserved by residents, during the 1930s, Yuldash Akhundboboev—one of the prominent leaders of the republic at the time—visited the area in connection with the establishment of a new administrative district. It is believed that he recommended Porasht as the prospective district center during this visit.

When the district was officially established, the village of Baghdan—owing to its more advantageous geographical location—was selected as the administrative center. This decision was influenced by the relatively small population of Porasht and its distance from major transportation routes. Nevertheless, the newly formed district retained the name of the original village, preserving *Farish* as its official designation.

Results and discussion. The data collected during our field ethnographic research conducted in May, June, and August of 2024, along with the findings presented in the monograph by geographers K. Khakimov and O. Adilova, suggest that the name of the village *Porasht* served as the basis for the emergence of the current toponym *Forish*. In our view, oral tradition and the

dynamic, dialect-based nature of spoken language play a significant role in the formation of place names. In the local dialect, the village name is frequently pronounced as *Porash*, with the final “t” dropped [6]. From this perspective, it is plausible that the name evolved from *Porash* to *Porish*, and eventually to *Forish*, due to phonetic shifts common in Uzbek pronunciation. After the village name was adopted for the newly established district, the original settlement came to be officially referred to as *Eski Forish* (Old Forish).

Professor Kuchkar Hakimov notes that "the names of the villages Porasht, Andagin, and Ukhum in the Forish district date back to the early centuries of the Common Era. These toponyms originate from the ancient Sogdian language, which is now considered extinct. Despite the passage of time, they have been preserved—either in their original form or with minor phonetic alterations—in several regions that once belonged to the historical state of Ustrushana, including the present-day districts of Zamin, Bakhmal, Yangiabad, as well as parts of Forish and Gallaorol [7]."

According to Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor N. Nurnazarov, the term *Porasht* originates from the ancient Sogdian language, where *po* means "front" or "foothills," and *rasht* translates as "hill" or "mound." This interpretation aligns with historical accounts indicating that, prior to the 18th century, the village of *Porasht* was situated deeper within the mountainous terrain. Today, only remnants of an ancient mound mark the location of the original settlement, providing archaeological evidence that supports this etymological and historical perspective.

Farish district is situated within the Majrumsay irrigation system, located in the western part of the Jizzakh oasis. It encompasses the basins of Ilonchisay, Kyzylkiyasay, Ukhumsay, and Soloklisay, all of which are regulated by the historic Khanbandi dam. The district has historically faced significant challenges due to the near absence of perennial water sources, resulting in chronic water shortages that have hindered agricultural development. However, the construction of the Khanbandi dam in the 10th century, during the Middle Ages, along with the establishment of water control structures, played a crucial role in partially mitigating these issues and improving irrigation in the region [8].

The larger villages in Farish district are primarily situated in the mountainous and foothill regions, with several settlements—such as Majrum, Andagen, Asraf, Ukhum, Khoyat Porasht, Ilonchisay, Osmonsay, Baland Osman, Garasha, and Karaabdal—forming a linear pattern along the Nurota foothills. This arrangement is largely a result of the population's settlement along both large and small streams and rivers, areas that are more accessible to water resources. The proximity to water sources has been crucial for supporting agricultural and horticultural activities, making these locations more favorable for farming [9].

The historical and ethnographic route through the Jizzakh-Forish region and the Aydar-Arnasay lake system offers tourists an immersive experience, guiding them through significant sites such as the Yuqarisay (Soyibolo) basin in the Eski Forish (Porasht) village of the Forish district. The route also includes notable streams and gorges like Sigimsay, Ukhumsay, and Majrumsay, as well as the Uchmasay River flowing through Uchma village. Tourists can explore monuments with rich symbolic content, including anthropomorphic (hunter) and zoomorphic (mainly camel and argali) figures, as well as geometric motifs. The area is also home to remarkable natural landmarks, such as a two-thousand-year-old juniper tree (Eastern biota) along the Majrumsay River in the Nurota Mountains, 500-year-old mulberry and walnut groves, and the Ukhum observation point. Wildlife enthusiasts can visit Hayat village to see argali, while the

Porasht village boasts seven scenic waterfalls. The 10th-century Khanbandi dam in Band town, therapeutic mud in Tuzkan, and the picturesque Tuzkan Lake, surrounded by desert landscapes, further enhance the region's appeal. Additionally, the Mirzachol mineral waters and local medical facilities offer unique opportunities for health tourism, making this route an attractive destination for a variety of visitors.

The reserve, situated in the western part of the Jizzakh region, specifically within the Forish district, is positioned on the northern slope of the Nurota Mountain range. Established in 1975, the reserve spans an area of 17,752 hectares, of which 2,599 hectares are covered by forests, as reported in 2001. The reserve's elevation ranges from 530 to 2,100 meters above sea level, providing a diverse ecological landscape that supports a variety of flora and fauna. This geographical and environmental diversity contributes to the reserve's significance in the conservation of natural habitats and biodiversity in the region.

The region is also distinguished by its remarkable natural landscapes and archaeological significance. Notably, it is home to various monuments, including ancient rock paintings depicting hunting scenes involving mountain sheep. These rock art images provide valuable insights into the historical and cultural practices of the area's early inhabitants. Additionally, the region is recognized for its population of mountain sheep (Arhar), with the current number exceeding 500 individuals. This rich cultural and ecological heritage underscores the region's importance as both a natural and historical site of significant interest.

The stone inscriptions found in the village of Okhum, located near the reserve, are believed to date back to the 3rd–2nd centuries BCE and the 1st–8th centuries CE. Archaeological investigations indicate that during these periods, numerous settlements were established along the basins of the Sangzor, Zaminsuv, and other mountain streams. These communities actively cultivated the surrounding fertile lands, contributing to the region's early socio-economic development [10].

Okhum is one of the largest villages situated in the Farish Mountains. According to various historical sources, the Middle and Upper Okhum mounds represent some of the earliest known settlements in the area. In contrast, the mounds of Bozorjoy, Sultani Miyana, and Tabakdeh are believed to have emerged approximately 200 years ago. More recent settlements, including Hayati Poyon, Mula, Sirtikon, and Mushi Biryani, were established between the late 1940s and the 1980s.

The Forish district is notable for its rich agrotourism potential, particularly in the areas of horticulture and viticulture adapted to the region's hilly and mountainous terrain. Grape cultivation is especially well-developed, with numerous indigenous varieties such as *black currant*, *husyni*, *toypi*, *maska*, *chillaki*, and *sultoni*, all of which have adapted to the local natural conditions. Grape farming is widespread across nearly all villages in the district. Local communities traditionally produce raisins and molasses from grapes, both of which are staple elements of the regional cuisine [11].

According to ethnographer B. Kh. Karmisheva, local gardeners practice a unique land-use strategy by planting alfalfa among the grapevines during the first three years before the vines begin to bear fruit—a method not commonly observed elsewhere. She notes that 24 distinct grape varieties are cultivated in the area [12]. These findings highlight the deep-rooted traditions and long-standing expertise of the Forish district's population in horticulture and viticulture, reflecting their historical and cultural connection to the land.

Historical sources and archival records indicate that, at the beginning of the 20th century, over thirty grape varieties were cultivated in the Samarkand region, including the adjacent Farish district. Among the most renowned were the highly productive *chillaki* and the sweet *charos*, as well as *black and white kishmish*, *Kattakurgan*, *hussaini*, *maska*, *shakarak*, and *sultani*. Further evidence of the region's rich viticultural heritage can be found in Issue No. 5 of the newspaper *Ashabad* (1902), which reported the presence of 24 distinct grape varieties known for their sweetness in the Zarafshan Valley, particularly in the Jizzakh and Khujand uezds [13]. These accounts underscore the historical depth and diversity of grape cultivation in the area and reaffirm the Farish district's strong potential in the sphere of agrotourism.

Today, many of these traditional grape varieties continue to be cultivated. In the villages of Sayyod, Balandasmon, Osmonsay, Ilonlisay, Korabdol, Garasha, and Okhum within the Forish district, both historical and newly developed local grape varieties are grown. These grapes are not only preserved as part of the region's agricultural heritage but are also actively marketed in local bazaars, contributing to the district's economy and enhancing its appeal as a destination for agrotourism.

In the Forish district of the Jizzakh region, a total of 33 cultural heritage sites have been placed under state protection. These include 15 archaeological sites, 14 architectural landmarks, and 4 monuments of monumental art. Among the most significant are the archaeological sites of Gumbaz-Oqtepa (Oyim), Abdullakhtepa, and Band (the historic Khanbandi water dam), as well as religious and spiritual landmarks such as the Hassan Ota shrine and the Mavlano Muhammad Sharif (Girihshok) khanaqah and mosque. These heritage sites play a vital role in the promotion and development of tourism in the region, reflecting its rich historical and cultural legacy.

The Forish district is also home to numerous sacred sites and shrines that reflect its deep historical roots and significant tourism potential. Among these are the shrines of Mawlana Muhammad Sharif, Hazrati Zainulabidin, Khoja Baghbon Ota, Hazrati Eshon Khalifa, and Narvan Ota. These sites, many of which date back to ancient times, serve not only as important religious and spiritual landmarks but also as key attractions for cultural and pilgrimage tourism in the region.

The Muhammad Sharif Mosque, also known as the Mavlano Girih Kushod Mosque, is located in the southern part of the Kurgan neighborhood in the village of Garasha. This historic mosque is named after Muhammad Sharif, a prominent figure and spiritual successor of the Khoja Ahmad Yassavi sufism ideas. Dating back to the 12th century, the mosque holds significant cultural and religious importance, representing the enduring influence of Sufi traditions in the region and contributing to the spiritual heritage and tourism appeal of the Forish district.

The shrine of *Khoja Bogbon Ota* is situated in the village of Qaratash in the Farish district. Historical records trace the origins of this sacred site to the 1270s of the 12th century. Revered for its spiritual significance, the shrine reflects the enduring legacy of Islamic devotion and local religious traditions. It remains an important pilgrimage destination and contributes to the cultural and historical tourism potential of the region.

Located just above the platform where pilgrims traditionally gather, there is a cave believed to have been the dwelling place of Khoja Baghbon Ota. The pathway leading to the cave gradually narrows, eventually becoming so tight that only a single person can pass through at a time. Navigating this narrow passageway brings visitors into the depths of the cave, where three chambers are hidden in the darkness.

The Khoja Baghbon Ota shrine is surrounded by numerous legends, many of which are deeply ingrained in local folklore. Pilgrims, especially local residents, have long held the belief that the shrine holds powerful healing properties. It is said that childless couples and individuals suffering from various ailments visit the shrine with sincere intentions, seeking blessings and spiritual healing. One of the key practices at the site involves drinking from the spring water, which is believed to possess curative qualities, offering hope for those in need of physical and emotional restoration.

The shrine of Hazrati Zaynulobiddin is located in the village of Mojurum in the Forish district, bordering the Nurota district of the Navoi region.

The person who took the name Zayn al-Abd al-Din was the 24th descendant of Hazrat Hasan ibn Ali Abu Talib, that is, the 25th descendant of Hazrat Ali - Zayn al-Abd al-Din (born approximately in 895 and died in 915), who was martyred in his youth on the Nagur road in front of his father by road-breakers.

Along with pilgrimage tourism, ecotourism activities have also been established in the district. It should be noted that the natural climate of the district, ecological situation, and unique nature such as mountains and steppes have prospects for the development of rural tourism (ethnographic tourism) in Uchkuloch, Ukhum, Porasht, and Kattabog'don neighbourhood areas.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the harmonious development of both historical and natural resources in the Forish district has the potential to create mutually enriching types of tourism. By integrating these diverse resources into well-organized tourist routes, it will be possible to offer comprehensive services to visitors. This approach not only enhances the region's appeal as a tourist destination but also opens up new economic opportunities for the local population and entrepreneurs, fostering sustainable development and cultural preservation in the process.

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